

TASKS OF EDUCATING YOUNG PEOPLE IN THE SPIRIT OF MILITARY PATRIOTISM

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The command of the security forces of categorized objects.

Annotation: *This article is devoted to the study of the process of educating our youth in the spirit of military patriotism, the main strength of our country, the main pillar of our development, and the main priorities in educating in the spirit of military patriotism. At the same time, we will introduce the system of educating young people in the spirit of military patriotism, as well as some of the problems that hinder the education of young people in the spirit of military patriotism today.*

Keywords: *Homeland, patriotic, military, concept, veteran, servant, hand-to-hand combat, summer biathlon, sniper.*

Аннотация: *Данная статья посвящена изучению процесса воспитания молодежи в духе воинского патриотизма, главной силы нашей страны, главной опоры нашего развития, основных приоритетов воспитания в духе воинского патриотизма. При этом мы представим систему воспитания молодежи в духе воинского патриотизма, а также некоторые проблемы, препятствующие сегодня воспитанию молодежи в духе воинского патриотизма.*

Ключевые слова: *Родина, патриотический, военный, концепция, ветеран, служащий, рукопашный бой, летний биатлон, снайпер.*

Introduction. In educating the youth in the spirit of military patriotism, it is impossible to form the young generation, regardless of nationality, language, profession and social origin, to form loyalty to the Fatherland, to fulfill their civic duties and constitutional obligations, to protect the interests of society and state. multi-level, systematic, targeted and coordinated activities of the state bodies, public associations and organizations. The activities of educational institutions play a key role in educating young people in the spirit of military patriotism. This is due to the fact that most of the youth's time is spent in pre-school education, general secondary schools, secondary special, vocational and higher education institutions.

Literature analysis and methodology. A number of measures are being taken in our country to educate young people in the spirit of military patriotism. The reason is that educating young people in the spirit of military patriotism is a priority of state policy is one of the directions. In the current context of globalization, at a time of rapid development of information and communication technologies, the current challenges and ways to address them in the education of young people in the spirit of military patriotism, government and non-governmental organizations, families, neighborhoods,

educational institutions determine the role and importance of cooperation in this area, taking into account national and international legal norms.

In accordance with the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 140 of February 23, 2018, the "Concept of educating young people in the spirit of military patriotism" was developed. The purpose of educating young people in the spirit of military patriotism is to be active in various sectors of society, especially in the civil service, to be loyal to the Constitution and military duty in a peaceful and military environment, to the fate of their country and people. to form important qualities such as high responsibility and accountability for.

Results. The main tasks of educating young people in the spirit of military patriotism are:

in the spirit of the national idea and devotion to the Motherland, to instill in their hearts and minds that the defense of the Motherland is an honorable and sacred duty;

selflessly for the independence and development of our ancient history and culture, to form a sense of belonging to them, to strengthen confidence in the strength and potential of our national army;

the need for physically strong and spiritually mature young people in our national army, that military service is a sacred duty for every citizen of Uzbekistan, as well as theoretical and practical skills in this area;

people the skills to approach the political and social processes taking place around us and in the world based on our national interests, ideological immunity against various internal and external threats ;

quick and independent decision-making in any difficult situation, educating young people with the skills to effectively use modern military equipment;

of Uzbekistan not only in the military sphere, but in all spheres of life, to be selfless for the country - this is the need of today to instill in the minds of young people through real-life examples and effective means.

Discussion . Based on the tasks set out in the " Concept of educating young people in the spirit of military patriotism", I think it is appropriate to carry out the following tasks to educate students of higher education in the spirit of military patriotism:

essence of the ongoing reforms in the Armed Forces of the country and to further strengthen the respect and attention to the military profession among students, the "Spiritual Hours" focused on the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan, military profession and military life. systematic organization of lessons on topics;

secondly, on the occasion of the Defender of the Fatherland Day on January 14, servicemen with rich life experience and veterans of the Armed Forces, servicemen and war veterans who have won various competitions and contests in science, culture and sports. , scheduled meetings with students with the participation of other combatants, roundtables, various quizzes, military sports competitions among conscripts and students on

conscription and contract military service, essays on military issues organization of competitions, spiritual and educational events;

Thirdly, on the occasion of May 9, the Day of Remembrance and Honor, the importance of courage, bravery and courage shown by veterans of World War II and post-war labor, servicemen and law enforcement officers who died in the line of duty during the years of independence organization of cultural, educational and patriotic events to explain, propagandize and promote among students, to organize visits of students to their places of residence with the participation of leaders in order to congratulate them and get information about their condition;

in educational institutions, including the opening of clubs in sports such as "Hand-to-hand combat", "Summer Biathlon", "Sniper" and ensuring the participation of students;

close to the educational institution, to develop and implement a plan of cooperation in patriotic education;

Sixth, to ensure the participation of servicemen of the Armed Forces in the spiritual and educational activities of the educational institution and the exchange of experience in the organization of spiritual and educational activities with servicemen.

Conclusion. The role of educational institutions in educating young people in the spirit of military patriotism is enormous. In the education of students of higher education institutions in the spirit of military patriotism, the spiritual-educational and educational activities carried out at the educational institution are carried out through activities organized in cooperation with the military.

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